

DNA Methylation Signatures in Placenta Associated with Prenatal Air Pollution Exposure and Potential Impact on Birth Outcomes: A Study of Three Prospective Cohorts

"DNA Methylation Signatures in Placenta Associated with Prenatal Air Pollution Exposure and Potential Impact on Birth Outcomes: A Study of Three Prospective Cohorts" was published in May 2024 in *The Lancet Planetary Health*, which has an Impact Factor of 24. Prenatal exposure to air pollution (PAPE) has been linked to a wide range of adverse birth and childhood outcomes, yet data on its impact on the placental epigenome, which may regulate physiological functions and influence child development, remains limited. This study aimed to investigate the relationship between prenatal exposure to air pollutants and changes in placental DNA methylation patterns and to explore potential windows of susceptibility and sex-specific alterations.

The study found that exposure to air pollutants (NO₂, PM₁₀, and PM_{2.5}) during pregnancy significantly influenced epigenetic changes (DNA methylation, DNAm) in infants, as confirmed by the analysis of multiple CpG sites. The median exposure during pregnancy was 19.7 µg/m³ for NO₂, 18.1 µg/m³ for PM₁₀, and 12.1 µg/m³ for PM_{2.5}. Exposure to NO₂ in the first and third trimesters showed a negative correlation, while no such correlation was observed for PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}. The average pollutant concentrations in the second trimester were most strongly correlated with exposure across the entire pregnancy.

Population analysis identified four CpG sites significantly associated with pollutant exposure, one of which, near the NLRP6 gene, was positively associated with NO₂ exposure in the third trimester. Sex-stratified analysis revealed 650 CpG sites associated with pollutant exposure, including 150 for girls and 469 for boys. NO₂ showed the strongest association with CpG sites in both sexes, though boys had more sex-specific CpG sites related to exposure. For girls, most differentially methylated positions (DMPs) were associated with exposure in the third trimester, whereas for boys, the associations were more prominent with exposure throughout pregnancy and in the first trimester.

Sex-specific differential methylation regions (DMRs) were also identified, including one on the Y chromosome and 22 on the X chromosome in boys. Some of these were linked to the development of the nervous and immune systems. For the entire population, 28 DMRs were associated with genes related to neurodevelopment, immune development, and metabolism, including four DMRs linked to imprinted genes such as FOXP1 and OTX1.

Further analyses revealed associations between some DMPs and birth outcomes, such as birth weight and gestational length. CpGs associated with longer pregnancies were positively correlated with exposure to air pollution (PAPE). For girls, 71% of the associations involved body length and head circumference, while for boys, DNA

methylation at CpGs was linked to gestational length and birth weight. For PM2.5, exposure was associated with lower methylation and lower birth weight.

Region-based analyses identified 28 DMRs related to various pathways, including neuro- and immunological pathways, as well as metabolic pathways. Specific sex-related pathways were identified, such as calcium signaling and neurexin-neurologin pathways in girls, and extracellular matrix organization in boys. The findings were robust to various confounding factors and demonstrated associations between genes and newborn health, highlighting their potential implications for growth and neurocognitive development.

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Johanna Lepeule is a researcher and environmental epidemiologist, with expertise in air pollution and its impact on human health. She is affiliated with the French National Institute of Health and Medical Research (Inserm). Her research focuses on studying the effects of environmental exposures, particularly air pollution, on respiratory and cardiovascular health, as well as on the long-term effects of these exposures, including aging and chronic diseases. Index Hirsch 44.

Journal

The Lancet

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